

of $[\text{Rh}(\text{AmuH}^+)_2(\text{CN}^-)]_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, a medium band at 570 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 450 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Rh-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Rh-C}}$, respectively.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Alkanals by Hexacyanoferrate(III) catalysed by Osmium(VIII)

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KINETICS of oxidation of ethanal, propanal and n-butanal by hexacyanoferrate(III) in sodium carbonate-bicarbonate buffer have been studied. The reaction is zero order in oxidant, first order with respect to both alkanal and Os^{VIII} , and the order with respect to alkali has been found to be ≈ 0.5 . The data suggest that the anion of the hydrate of alkanal is involved in the oxidation. The thermodynamic parameters ΔE , PZ and ΔS^* were evaluated.

A review of literature shows that some work has been done on the kinetic studies of oxidation of alkanals under acidic conditions^{1,2} and ethanal

under alkaline conditions³. It was therefore thought fruitful to undertake kinetic studies of oxidation of a series of alkanals by hexacyanoferrate(III). This communication presents data on the OsO_4 -catalysed oxidation of ethanal, propanal and n-butanal.

Experimental

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (E. Merk, A.R.), ethanal (AnalaR), propanal (Riedel), n-butanal (Fluka A.G.), osmium tetroxide (Johnson and Mathey) were used. All other chemicals used were either A.R. or G.R. grade. The catalyst was prepared by dissolving a known weight of OsO_4 in 0.05 M KOH solution.

The reaction was studied in presence of carbonate-bicarbonate buffer solution (prepared by mixing equal volumes of 0.025 M solutions of each sodium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate). The reaction was carried out in an adequately thermostated cell of a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter using filter no. 42. The unconsumed hexacyanoferrate(III) was estimated after known intervals of time without disturbing the reaction mixture.

Results and Discussion

The rate of oxidation is found to be of zero order in [hexacyanoferrate(III)] and independent of the initial concentration of oxidant (Table 1).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF HEXACYANOFERRATE(III)

[Alkanal] = 3.93×10^{-3} M, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 8.33 \times 10^{-4}$ M, $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]^{**} = 4.16 \times 10^{-3}$ M, pH = 10.5, Temp. = 35°

$[\text{Fe}(\text{ON})_6^{3-}] \times 10^4$ M	$K_0 \times 10^7$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹		
	Ethanal*	Propanal**	n-Butanal**
3.93	7.40	11.26	5.29
3.00	6.66	11.22	4.87
2.66	6.85	11.60	5.95
2.33	6.66	10.59	4.77
2.00	6.66	10.61	4.40

The first order dependence on [substrate] is established by fairly constant values of $K_0/[\text{substrate}]$ (Table 2). OsO_4 catalyses the reaction. Constant values of $K_0/[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ (Table 3) and linear plot of $\log K_0$ vs $\log [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ with a slope of unity shows first order dependence of the rate on $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$. The rate of oxidation marginally increases with the increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$. A plot of $\log K_0$ vs $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ is linear with a slope of 0.5, suggesting half order in alkali. The values of activation parameters (Table 6) are close to the values given by Bakore and Narain⁹, suggesting C-H bond cleavage in the rate determining step.

From the fact that hexacyanoferrate is consumed but shows zero order dependence on $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$, it is reasonable to assume that hexacyanoferrate(III) does not react directly with substrate and its action

is delayed until after the rate determining step. The similarity of the rate laws to methanal, ethanal, propanal and n-butanal suggests that the reaction mechanism does not involve enolisation. The plot

and n-butanal proceed via anion of the alkanal hydrate. This is in sharp contrast to the observation of Pandey and Singh³ who argued enolisation as the rate determining step without the supporting

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF ALKANAL

[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 3.33 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Os^{VIII}] = 8.93 × 10⁻⁵ M, [Os^{VIII}]^{**} = 4.16 × 10⁻⁵ M, pH = 10.5, Temp. = 35°

[Alkanal] × 10 ³ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹			K ₀ /[Alkanal] × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹		
	Ethanal*	Propanal*	n-Butanal**	Ethanal*	Propanal*	n-Butanal**
3.33	7.40	11.26	5.29	2.22	3.39	1.59
2.67	6.06	9.31	4.16	2.27	3.49	1.56
2.00	4.10	7.17	3.41	2.05	3.58	1.70
1.33	2.81	4.73	2.48	2.11	3.55	1.87
0.67	1.67	2.36	1.18	2.35	3.54	1.76

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF CATALYST

[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 3.33 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Alkanal] = 3.33 × 10⁻³ M, pH = 10.5, Temp. = 35°

Ethanal			Propanal			n-Butanal		
[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ⁵ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	K ₀ /[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ⁵ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	K ₀ /[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ⁵ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	K ₀ /[Os ^{VIII}] × 10 ³ s ⁻¹
10.0	8.93	0.89	4.16	11.26	2.71	5.00	6.57	1.31
9.16	8.09	0.88	3.75	10.04	2.68	4.58	5.80	1.27
8.33	7.40	0.89	3.33	8.96	2.69	4.16	5.29	1.27
7.50	6.71	0.89	2.91	7.86	2.70	3.75	4.81	1.28
6.67	5.97	0.90	2.50	6.64	2.65	3.33	4.21	1.26

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH CONCENTRATION OF ALKALI

[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 3.33 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Alkanal] = 3.33 × 10⁻³ M, [Os^{VIII}] = 8.93 × 10⁻⁵ M, [Os^{VIII}]^{**} = 4.16 × 10⁻⁵ M, Temp. = 35°

[Alkali] × 10 ³ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹		
	Ethanal*	Propanal**	n-Butanal**
0.893	7.92	12.37	8.40
1.667	10.84	16.77	11.62
2.500	13.68	20.32	13.94
3.330	15.67	22.54	16.66
4.167	17.73	27.25	18.49

TABLE 5—VARIATION OF REACTION RATE WITH IONIC STRENGTH

[Fe(CN)₆³⁻] = 3.33 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Alkanal] = 3.33 × 10⁻³ M, [Os^{VIII}] = 8.93 × 10⁻⁵ M, [Os^{VIII}]^{**} = 4.16 × 10⁻⁵ M, pH = 10.5, Temp. = 35°

[KNO ₃] × 10 ³ M	K ₀ × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹		
	Ethanal*	Propanal**	n-Butanal**
0.833	7.94	11.78	5.71
1.667	8.23	12.40	5.83
2.500	9.36	13.04	5.94
3.333	9.89	13.87	6.28
4.167	9.83	14.46	7.54

TABLE 6—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

	ΔE [‡] kcal	PZ s ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] e.u.
Ethanal	11.62	1.66 × 10 ⁶	-30.95
Propanal	10.03	3.54 × 10 ⁵	-33.97
Butanal	10.48	3.57 × 10 ⁵	-33.95

of log K₀/[substrate] vs log R₀ is non linear and the rate of oxidation is about 60 times faster than the rate of enolisation (R_e). This provide sound basis to assume that oxidation of ethanal, propanal

and n-butanal proceed via anion of the alkanal hydrate. The fact that reaction shows a slight positive salt effect which is indicative of reaction between two similarly charged ions. In the light of above data, it is proposed that a complex is formed between anion of the hydrate and osmate ion, which slowly decomposes into products followed by fast reaction between the reduced Os^{VI} and hexacyanoferrate(III). Alkanal is represented in the mechanism by RCH₂CHO, where R stands for H, CH₃ and C₂H₅.

Applying steady state treatment and assuming $K_2 \ll K_{-1}$, the rate of reaction is given by the equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{K_{eq} \cdot K_2 K_3 [\text{Alkanal}][\text{OH}^-][\text{O}_8^{\text{VIII}}]}{K_{-2}}$$

The rate equation satisfactorily explains all the observed kinetic features except the fractional order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$, an observation similar to the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes⁴⁻⁶ by permanganate. The fractional order with respect to hydroxyl ion concentration suggests a negative centre at the site of attack or a free radical. A negative acrylamide test excludes the possibility of free radical, thus involvement of negative centres at the site of attack, *i.e.* mono-anion of the alkanal hydrate is the only possibility.

The fractional order with respect to alkali shows that there are two reactive species, *i.e.* alkanal hydrate and anion of the hydrate as indicated by the above equation.

The first order rate constant $K_2/[\text{substrate}]$, for methanal, ethanal, propanal and n-butanal are respectively 3.24, 2.20, 3.50 and $1.69 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which shows that the substituted alkanals with electron donating substituents react faster than ethanal (substituted).

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Studies on Aminoacetamides. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(arylamidomethylamino)diphenylsulphones

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AMINOACETAMIDE derivatives have been found to possess a wide variety of physiological activities¹⁻⁹. Keeping this in view, some new amino-

acetamide derivatives of type 1 were synthesised by condensing 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone with monochloromethyl acetate and then treated with sodium hydroxide to get *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone. This was then condensed with thionyl chloride and different aromatic amines. The compounds were characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectroscopic data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) were recorded on a EM 360 (60 MHz) spectrometer.

p,p'-Bis (carbmethoxymethylamino) diphenylsulphone : 4,4'-Diaminodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) dissolved in dimethylformamide (30 ml) was added to monochloromethyl acetate (0.02 mol) and refluxed for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (68%), m.p. 156° (Found : C, 55.05 ; H, 5.04 ; N, 7.10. C₁₈H₂₀N₂O₆S calcd for : C, 55.10 ; N, 7.14%).

p,p'-Bis (carboxymethylamino) diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carbomethoxymethylamino)-diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) and dilute sodium hydroxide (10 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (62%), m.p. 98° (Found : C, 52.70 ; H, 4.32 ; N, 7.63. C₁₈H₁₆N₂O₆S calcd. for : C, 52.74 ; H, 4.39 ; N, 7.69%).

p,p'-Bis (phenylamidomethylamino) diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethylamino)-diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol) dissolved in dioxane (10 ml) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess of thionyl chloride was removed by distillation. The product obtained was refluxed with aniline and 2-3 drops of pyridine using dioxane (10 ml) as solvent for a further 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol. (78%), m.p. > 360° (Found : C, 63.33 ; H, 5.02 ; N, 10.85. C₂₈H₂₈N₄O₄S calcd. for : C, 63.36 ; H, 5.05 ; N, 10.89%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 375 (SO₂ sym. str.), 1 150 (SO₂ sym. str.), 3 325 (NH str.), 1 640 (C=O str.), 1 520 (NH def. +C-N str.) and 1 300 cm⁻¹ (NH def. +C-N str.) ; δ (TMS ; DMSO-*d*₆) 2.68 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.5 (4H, s, CH₂), 4.2 (4H, s, NH) and 7.9-6.6 (16H, m, Ar-H).

Similarly, other aminoacetamide derivatives were prepared. The physical data are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity : Aminoacetamide derivatives were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method⁹. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 100 μg using